

Impact of Yoga on Attention of School Going Children

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Abstract

The present study aimed to examine the impact of yoga in enhancing the span of attention among school-going children aged 14 to 16 years. A total of 60 participants were chosen from Saraswati Vidya Mandir Senior Secondary School in Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh. They were divided into two equal groups: a yoga group and a control group, with 30 students in each. The experimental group underwent a structured yoga program for a duration of six weeks, while the control group followed their regular school routine without any yogic intervention. To assess changes in attention span, a wooden slider tachistoscope was used for all subjects at both pre- and post-intervention stages. To test the significance of the results, a paired sample t-test was applied at the 0.05 level of significance. The results showed a significant improvement in the attention span of the yoga group ($t(29) = 9.146$, $p < 0.05$), while no notable change was found in the control group ($t(29) = 0.701$, $p > 0.05$). These results suggest that selected yogic practices positively influence the attention span of adolescents. The null hypothesis, which stated that there would be no significant impact of yoga on attention span, was rejected. The study highlights the potential of yoga as an effective tool to support cognitive development in school-aged children.

Keywords

Attention, Span of Attention, Sustained Attention, Yoga, Memory, Concentration.

Introduction

In the current digital world, young students are surrounded by distractions like smartphones, online games, and fast-paced lifestyles. These distractions often reduce their ability to pay attention in school and affect learning outcomes (Joshi, S.C. et al., 2022). Attention can be defined as the mental process of concentrating on specific information while ignoring other stimuli (Posner & Rothbart, 2007). The span of attention refers to the length of time a person can focus on a task without distracted (Hillman, C.H. et al., 2006). A reduced attention span has been linked with poor academic results, behavior problems, and even mental stress (Cardoso-Leite, P. et al., 2021). Development of the brain continues between the ages of 10–25 years, though the size of the brain remains the same, whereas creases or folds keep increasing. Frontal lobe maturation goes on until prefrontal cortex development is accomplished, which is mainly responsible for all executive functions of the nervous system, including attention.

Lack of attention among children causes their perception of understanding and the environment to become meaningless and perplexing. Cognitive processes like comprehension and reasoning heavily depend on attention in academics (Ganpat, T. et al., 2013). Attention is not a single ability but includes sustained attention, selective attention, divided attention, and alternating attention (Petersen, S.E. & Posner, M.I., 2012). Sustained and selective attention are most relevant for academic settings. Attention span contains many processes, such as visual scanning, mental flexibility, sustained attention, psychomotor speed, and information processing speed (Hillman C.H., et al. 2006). Mental flexibility, working memory, selective attention, and sustained attention are key qualities for success in school and work. They help children focus on specific targets in their environment while avoiding distractions over time. This focus is strongly influenced by the amount of learning.

Objective of study

1. To assess the effect of a six-week yoga intervention on the attention span of school-going boys aged 14 to 16 years.
2. To examine whether selected yogic practices (Asana, Pranayama, and Dhyana) can significantly improve attention span.
3. To contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting yoga as a non-medical tool for enhancing attention span in school going children of 14 to 16 years old boys.

Review of Literature

A child's attention span can be affected by many internal and external factors. Internally, factors like physical health, emotional state, mental fatigue, nutrition, and sleep quality play a major role in how well attention is sustained (Lim, J. & Dinges, D.F., 2010; Wassenaar, T.M., et al., 2019). Family conditions and the home environment also contribute to a greater extent on the reduction of attention span in childhood, as it helps children to get oriented and examine objects in their environment. The financial background of the child has also been seen as a reason for reduced sustained attention due to peer pressure caused by social isolation and lower confidence (Oken B.S., et al., 2006). Externally, factors such as classroom environment, noise levels, teacher communication style, and digital distractions like excessive mobile use can reduce attention span (Mincera, A.G., 2024).

There is increasing interest in non-medical, natural methods to improve attention in children. One such method is yoga, an age-old practice that includes physical postures (Asana), breathing activities (Pranayama), and meditation (Dhyana). Studies have shown that yoga does not only benefit physical health, but also helps the brain by improving focus, self-control, and emotional balance (Subramanya, P. & Telles, S., 2009; Ranjani, H., et al., 2023). A wide range of research supports yoga's positive effects on cognitive functions such as attention and memory, especially in school children and teenagers. For example, (Panagar, T. and Kaur, D., 2024) found that just 30 days of Super Brain Yoga significantly improved sustained attention in adolescents aged 13 to 15 years. (Ranjani, H., et al., 2023) conducted a large study across India with 2,000 students and reported better attention and memory performance in the yoga group after a 17-week intervention. (Joshi, R., et al., 2024) observed improvements not only in attention span but also in breathing capacity in school children following four weeks of yoga practice. (Khunti, K., et al., 2022) observed improvements in reaction time and memory among students practicing yoga in urban school settings. (Jarraya, S., et al., 2019) tested mindfulness and yoga programs in classrooms and noted better classroom behavior and longer attention spans. (Caldarella, P. and Moya, M.S., 2022) reported that yoga significantly reduced distractions and increased attentional focus in middle school children. Research by (Jarraya, M., et al., 2019) in kindergartens showed that yoga improved visual attention and reduced hyperactivity in five-year-old children. In a different study, (Gothe, N. and McAuley, E., 2015) showed that just eight weeks of Hatha yoga led to enhanced executive functioning and attention in participants. (Subramanya, P., & Telles, S., 2009) confirmed that even short daily yoga sessions across Indian schools increased concentration and reduced mental fatigue. (Field, T., 2016) suggested that children with attention disorders such as ADHD experienced better focus and less anxiety after practicing yoga and breathing techniques. Yoga practices like pranayama and asana have been found to activate the parasympathetic nervous system, reduce cognitive fatigue, and improve prefrontal cortex functioning. These effects are important for managing attention (Shobana, R. et al., 2022; Villemure et al., 2015). (Ranjani, H., et al., 2023) found that alternate nostril breathing improves attention and enhances alpha wave activity in the brain, which is related to relaxed alertness and better focus.

These studies together demonstrate evidence supporting yoga as an effective tool for improving attention and cognitive abilities in young learners. This growing body of research shows that yoga could be an affordable, simple, and non-invasive way to help children focus better in their studies. However, most of these studies are either done on young children or over long durations. There is still a research gap when it comes to short-term, focused yoga interventions in adolescent students, especially those aged 14–16 years.

Methodology

This study was conducted at Saraswati Vidya Mandir Senior Secondary School, located in Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh. A total of 60 healthy students from classes 9 to 12, aged 14 to 16 years, were randomly selected as participants. They were then randomly assigned into two equal groups: Yoga Group (n = 30) and Control Group (n = 30). The intervention period lasted for six weeks, during the months of September and October 2023. Participants in the Yoga Group engaged in 60-minute yoga sessions, conducted five days a week, from 7:00 am to 8:30 am on the school premises. The Control Group did not participate in any structured yoga or physical training program during the intervention period. To examine the span of attention, a Tachistoscope (wooden falling door type) was used. This is a widely recognized and reliable instrument specifically designed to measure attention span in controlled settings. All participants were briefed in advance about the experimental procedure, and informed consent was obtained. They were clearly informed that their participation was voluntary, data would be kept anonymous, and they had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any stage without any consequence. To minimize bias, participants were kept blind to the group conditions. The test scale was explained to all students before the data collection process. On the days of testing (both pre- and post-intervention), students reported to the Atal Lab located on the school campus, between 7:00 am and 10:00 am. Data were collected from all participants before and after the 6-week intervention.

Yoga Intervention

The yoga programme was developed to examine whether regular yoga practice could enhance the attention span of school-going male students. It included loosening activity (Surya Namaskar), Prayer (Gayatri Mantra), selected asanas (Tadasana, Trikonasana, Paschimottanasana, Ardh-Matsyendrasana, Sarvangasana, Halasana, Chakrasana, Bhujangasana, Shalabhasana and Dhanurasana), Pranayama (Anulom Vilom and Brahmari), kriyas (Kapalbhati and Trataka), and Yoga Nidra. Surya Namaskar and Gayatri Mantra recitation prepared the body and mind at the beginning. Other Practices were chosen to stimulate proprioceptors, balance the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems, and reduce mental restlessness. Shavasana and Makarasana were performed between practices for relaxation. The programme was designed in consultation with experts and supervisor and conducted by qualified yoga instructors.

Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using paired sample t-tests to compare the pre-intervention and post-intervention scores within each group. This method was chosen to determine whether the yoga intervention had a statistically significant effect on attention span. In the last, descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to provide a clear summary of the quantitative variables, offering an easy-to-understand conclusion of the data distribution and trends.

Table 1: Comparison of mean between pre and post-test of the Yoga group of attention.

Data	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Mean Difference	T value	df	P value
Pre	12.80	30	1.669	0.305	1.433	9.146	29	<0.001
Post	14.23	30	1.194	0.218				

(Tabulated t-value = 2.045, level of significance = 0.05)

Table 1 shows a notable improvement in attention within the yoga group. The mean post-test score (14.23) was higher than the pre-test score (12.80), resulting in a mean difference of 1.433. The computed t-value (9.146) exceeds the tabulated t-value (2.045) at the 0.05 level, and the corresponding significance level ($p < 0.001$) is well below 0.05, confirming the result as statistically significant.

Table 2: Comparison of mean between pre and post-test of the control group of attention

Data	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Mean Difference	t-value	df	p-value
Pre	12.83	30	1.555	0.284	0.133	0.701	29	0.489
Post	12.97	30	1.299	0.237				

(Tabulated t-value = 2.045, level of significance = 0.05)

Table 2 shows a slight improvement in attention within the control group. The mean post-test score (12.97) was slightly higher than the pre-test score (12.83), resulting in a mean difference of +0.133. The computed t-value (0.701) is less than the tabulated t-value (2.045) at the 0.05 level, and the corresponding significance level ($p = 0.489$) is greater than 0.05, indicating that the result is not statistically significant.

Graph 1: Mean Difference of Yoga and Control Groups.

Result and Discussion

The analysis clearly demonstrates a significant improvement in the attention scores of participants in the yoga intervention group compared to their baseline scores. As shown in Table 1, the mean attention score increased from 12.80 (± 1.669) in the pre-test to 14.23 (± 1.194) in the post-test. The calculated t-value ($t = 9.146$) is considerably higher than the tabulated t-value (2.045) at a 0.05 level of significance, and the associated p-value ($p < 0.001$) indicates a highly significant difference.

On the other hand, the control group, presented in Table 2, showed only a slight, non-significant increase in mean attention score from 12.83 (± 1.555) to 12.97 (± 1.299). The calculated t-value ($t = 0.701$) is much lower than the tabulated t-value, and the p-value ($p = 0.489$) is greater than 0.05, therefore the difference is not statistically significant.

From this analysis, it can be inferred that a structured yoga intervention conducted for 60 minutes, five days a week over six weeks led to a statistically significant improvement in attention among school-going adolescents aged 14–16 years. In contrast, no meaningful change was observed in the control group that did not receive any yoga training. These results strongly support the effectiveness of yoga practices in enhancing attention span and cognitive focus in this age group.

Findings

Attention is a very important part of learning. It helps students understand, remember, and use information in their studies. This study was done to see if yoga could help improve the attention span of male students in school. The results clearly showed that students who practiced yoga for six weeks had a much better attention span than those who did not do yoga.

The improvement in the yoga group can be linked to how yoga affects the mind and body. Many past studies also support this idea. For example, (Oken, B.S., et al., 2006) found

that yoga and meditation can help the brain work faster and process information better. (Subramanya, P. and Telles, S., 2009) showed that yoga helps the brain focus by blocking unnecessary signals, which makes thinking clearer.

Yoga is a learning method with roots in India, aiming to bring the mind, body, and spirit together through three main parts: physical activities, breathing, and meditation. Yogasanas, which blend physical postures and proper breathing, help to keep the body balanced and the mind calm. They not only lower stress and anxiety but also improve concentration and focused attention. Holding a pose requires steady focus, which trains the brain to concentrate for longer periods.

By blending meditation with yoga's stress-relieving aspects, one can cultivate mental harmony. (Prakash, R., et al., 2010) showed that meditation activates the parasympathetic nervous system, which calms the mind and reduces stress. Such practice helps control unnecessary thoughts and supports mental stability. (Abadi, M.S. and S. Venkatesan, J.M., 2008) noted that focusing on a point during yoga practice improves overall focus in daily tasks too.

Other studies also found similar results. For example, (Panagar, T. and Kaur, D. 2024) showed that Super Brain Yoga increased attention in teenagers in just 30 days. (Ranjani, H., et al. 2023) found that students doing yoga for 17 weeks had better attention and memory. (Joshi, R., et al., 2024) observed that school children improved their attention span and breathing capacity after four weeks of yoga practice.

The positive effect seen in this study can also be explained by how yoga works at a deeper level in the body and brain. Practising asanas in a calm and steady way lowers muscle tension, quiets the sympathetic nervous system, and activates the parasympathetic system, creating a relaxed but alert state. When the posture is held comfortably, proprioceptors in the muscles and joints send signals to the brain to adjust muscle tone naturally, which helps the mind stay steady without extra effort. Electromyographic studies show that relaxed yoga postures reduce muscle effort and energy use, so students feel less tired and more focused. The gentle stretching in asanas improves blood circulation and keeps the body flexible and comfortable, which helps maintain mental calmness.

Pranayama, especially alternate nostril breathing, balances both sides of the nervous system by calming the sympathetic side and supporting the parasympathetic response. This makes breathing more efficient, calms emotions, and helps control distracting thoughts. Focusing on breathing trains the mind to stay present, which supports better attention in class and daily life.

Evidence of this concept is present in the ancient texts of yoga. The Hatha Yoga Pradipika (Chapter 2, Verse 2) says:

चले वाते चलं चित्तं निश्चले निश्चलं भवेत्।

योगी स्थाणुत्वमाप्नोति ततो वायुं निरोधयेत्॥

Chale vāte chalam chittam niśchale niśchalam bhavet |

Yogī sthāṇutvamāpnoti tato vāyum nirodhayet ||

Means, "When the breath moves, the mind moves. When the breath becomes steady, the mind becomes steady. So, the yogi should control the breath to steady the mind."

This verse explains that by controlling the breath through yoga, the mind also becomes calm and focused, which supports the findings of this study.

In this study, the mean score for attention increased a lot in the yoga group but hardly changed in the control group. The t-test value (9.146) was much higher than the required value, showing that this result is not just by chance but a real effect of yoga practice.

So, this research shows that even a short period of daily yoga and meditation can help students pay better attention in class. In today's world full of distractions, pressure, and stress, adding yoga to the school timetable could be a simple, low-cost way to help students improve their concentration and cope with stress.

However, this study also has some limits. It was done on a small number of students and for only six weeks. In the future, bigger studies with more students and longer yoga programs should be done to better understand these benefits and to explore how yoga can help in other areas of student life too.

Conclusion

The present study shows that regular yoga practice for six weeks has a positive effect on improving the attention span of school-going male students. The yoga group showed a significant increase in attention scores compared to the control group, which did not show any meaningful change. This suggests that yoga can be an effective, low-cost, and simple way to help students focus better and perform well in academics. Overall, integrating yoga into daily school life may support students' mental well-being and learning abilities.

**Suggestions for the
future Study**

It is recommended that schools include short, regular yoga sessions in the daily timetable to help students improve their attention and reduce stress. Parents should also motivate children to practice simple yoga at home to maintain these benefits. Teachers and school leaders should arrange proper training for safe practice. More research with larger groups and longer time frames is suggested to understand the full impact of yoga on students' attention and learning.

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